

Pathos

Open Science Impact Pathways

Deliverable 3.5

Data Management Plan Update

Deliverable Number and Name	D3.5 Data Management Plan Update
Due Date	29/02/2024
Delivery Date	11/04/2024 (Update: 10/11/2025)
Work Package	WP3
Type	DMP – Data Management Plan
Author	Petros Stavropoulos, Ioanna Grypari, Haris Papageorgiou, Erika Balsyte, Nicki Lisa Cole, Pedro Principe, Vincent Traag, Corinne Martin
Reviewers	Andrew Hoffman, Natalia Manola
Approved by	Ioanna Grypari
Dissemination Level	Public
Version	2.0
Number of Pages	102

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe framework programme under grant agreement No. 101058728. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

Revision History

VERSION	DATE	REASON	REVISED BY
0.5	15/02/2024	First Draft	All authors
0.7	21/03/2024	Peer Reviewed	Andrew Hoffman, Natalia Manola
0.8	28/03/2024	Second Draft	All authors
0.9	08/04/2024	Project Coordinator QA	Ioanna Grypari
1.0	11/04/2024	Final Draft	Petros Stavropoulos
2.0	10/11/2025	Update	Petros Stavropoulos

Table 1: Document Revision History

Table of Contents

Disclaimer	5
Abbreviations	6
Executive Summary	7
1. Data Management Plan	8
1.1. Input Datasets and Tools.....	8
1.1.1. OpenAIRE Research Graph Dump.....	8
1.1.2. OpenAIRE Research Graph: Dump of funded products.....	13
1.1.3. OpenAIRE Research Graph Dump: new collected projects.....	17
1.1.4. AI-Climate EU Collection of Projects and Publications enriched with FoS labels powered by SciNoBo.....	22
1.1.5. Covid-19 EU Collection of Projects and Publications enriched with FoS labels powered by SciNoBo.....	23
1.1.6. The Lens (lens.org).....	24
1.1.7. FCT funding streams and projects information - SciPROJ.....	27
1.1.8. CNRS - OpenEditions and HAL connexion logs	33
1.1.9. EP full-text data 2024	38
1.1.10. EuropePMC.....	39
1.1.11. Research Organization Registry (ROR.org)	39
1.1.12. CORD-19 Open Research Dataset	42
1.1.13. Semantic Scholar Academic Graph	45
1.1.14. PubMed	49
1.1.15. SciNoBo Toolkit.....	52
1.1.16. Gender Classification Model.....	55
1.1.17. DataStet Toolkit	57
1.1.18. Data Citation Corpus Data File	58
1.1.19. DataCite Public Data File.....	61

1.1.20.	OpenAlex.....	62
1.1.21.	Eurostat NACE Rev. 2.1.....	63
1.1.22.	IPinfo's Academic Research Program.....	65
1.1.23.	ElasticSearch and Kibana	67
1.2.	Output Datasets and Tools.....	69
1.2.1.	All Output Datasets	69
1.2.2.	Collaborations extracted from RCAAP based on the citation and network analysis	71
1.2.3.	Case study focus group data	72
1.2.4.	Mentions of ELIXIR resource names in patent applications (via lens.org).....	76
1.2.5.	Mentions of ELIXIR-supported publications in EuropePMC.....	79
1.2.6.	Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications Case Study Results and Indicators.....	83
1.2.7.	Impact of Open Access Colors on Topic Persistence Case Study Results and Indicators.....	86
1.2.8.	Bioinformatics job vacancies analysis.....	89
1.2.9.	Automated Nace Domain Classifier	90
1.2.10.	French Open Science Log Explorer	91
1.2.11.	Data from Scoping Review on Impact of Open Science	92
1.2.12.	Dataset – UniProt and RCAAP CBA Case Studies (PathOS Project).....	96
1.2.13.	Data for Deliverable D1.3 Key Impact Pathways for the Open Science Framework.....	98

Disclaimer

This document contains description of the PathOS project findings, work and products. Certain parts of it might be under partner Intellectual Property Right (IPR) rules so, prior to using its content please contact the consortium head for approval.

In case you believe that this document harms in any way IPR held by you as a person or as a representative of an entity, please do notify us immediately.

The authors of this document have taken any available measure in order to ensure that its content is accurate, consistent and lawful. However, neither the project consortium as a whole nor the individual partners that implicitly or explicitly participated in the creation and publication of this document hold any sort of responsibility that might occur as a result of using its content.

This publication has been produced with the assistance of the European Union. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the PathOS consortium and can in no way be taken as a reflection of the views of the European Union.

PathOS is a project funded by the European Union (Grant Agreement No 101058728).

Abbreviations

ANR	Agence National de la Research
API	Application Programming Interface
CC	Creative Commons ¹
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, Reusability
FCT	Foundation for Science and Technology
FoS	Fields of Science
FWF	Austrian Science Fund
HE	Horizon Europe
HRZZ	Croatian Science Foundation
IPCR	International Patent Classification
M	Month
NIH	National Institutes of Health
NSF	National Science Foundation
NWO	Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research
PID	Persistent Identifier
RCAAP	Repositório Científico de Acesso Aberto de Portugal
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal(s)
SNSF	Swiss National Science Foundation
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
WT	Wellcome Trust

¹ <https://creativecommons.org/>

Executive Summary

This document contains the Data Management Plan (DMP) of PathOS on M36 of the project. It has been created using the ARGOS service (<https://argos.openaire.eu>) an online tool for creating, managing and sharing DMPs and linking them with the research artifacts they correspond to. In the DMP, we describe the input (re-used) and output (created) datasets that will be used in the technical work of PathOS, following the principles of Open (whenever possible) and FAIR as outlined in the Grant Agreement.²

² The numbering of the questions skips in order to allow the updating of the DMP in the future (i.e. filling out questions for which the information is currently missing) via the Argos service.

1. Data Management Plan

1.1. Input Datasets and Tools

1.1.1. OpenAIRE Research Graph Dump

“The OpenAIRE Graph (formerly known as the OpenAIRE Research Graph) is one of the largest open scholarly record collections worldwide, key in fostering Open Science and establishing its practices in the daily research activities. Conceived as a public and transparent good, populated out of data sources trusted by scientists, the Graph aims at bringing discovery, monitoring, and assessment of science back in the hands of the scientific community.

Imagine a vast collection of research products all linked together, contextualised and openly available. For the past years OpenAIRE has been working to gather this valuable record. It is a massive collection of metadata and links between scientific products such as articles, datasets, software, and other research products, entities like organisations, funders, funding streams, projects, communities, and data sources.

As of today, the OpenAIRE Graph aggregates around 450Mi metadata records with links collecting from 2K data sources trusted by scientists, including:

- Open Access journals registered in DOAJ
- Crossref
- Unpaywall
- ORCID
- Microsoft Academic Graph
- Datacite

and repositories registered in OpenDOAR, re3data.org, FAIRSharing.org, and the EOSC Service Catalogue. Among these, prominent repositories such as:

- UKPubMed
- ArXiv
- HAL
- Zenodo
- Figshare
- Dryad
- Repec

After cleaning, deduplication, enrichment and full-text mining processes, the graph is analysed to produce statistics for the OpenAIRE MONITOR, the Open Science Observatory, made

discoverable via the OpenAIRE EXPLORE and programmatically accessible via OpenAIRE Public APIs. Last but not least, the Graph data are openly available and can be used by third-parties to create added value services. ³

In the context of PathOS, this dataset will be used in the following case studies:

- ELIXIR's Bioinformatics Resources (ELIXIR)
- Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP (UMINHO)
- Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence (ATHENA RC)
- Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications (ATHENA RC)

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

JSON-LD

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

237.3 GB packed

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To combine with other data
- Other

³ <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

The OpenAIRE Graph will be used to estimate open science impact indicators for case studies.

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

OpenAIRE

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry
- Other

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Data identifiers

DOI

DOI for dataset: 10.5281/zenodo.4201546

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

Please refer to https://zenodo.org/record/7492313#.Y_319HZBxPY for full details.

3.1.1.9 ARE METADATA HARVESTABLE?

Yes

Please refer to https://zenodo.org/record/7492313#.Y_319HZBxPY for full details.

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

<https://zenodo.org>

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

- Follows repository standards

- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal
- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

OpenAIRE Research Graph Dump

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Dataset will remain available from OpenAIRE.

All data is openly available, no identity will be ascertained

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

Dataset will remain available from OpenAIRE.

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CANNOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

Yes

Metadata are already available from OpenAIRE.

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

Metadata are already available from OpenAIRE.

3.2.3.4 WILL METADATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER THE DATASET / OUTPUT IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

Yes

Metadata are already available from OpenAIRE.

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

3.3.2 IF YOU CREATED THE VOCABULARY, WHERE CAN IT BE FOUND?

OpenAIRE documentation: <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/>

Sustainable Development Goals (SDG): <https://explore.openaire.eu/sdgs>

Fields of Science (FoS): <https://explore.openaire.eu/fields-of-science>

3.3.3 HAVE YOU APPLIED A STANDARD SCHEMA FOR YOUR (META)DATA?

Yes

DataCite Metadata Schema

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 WILL YOU PROVIDE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN?

Yes

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

No

This is provided by OpenAIRE.

3.4.5 IS PROVENANCE WELL DOCUMENTED?

Yes

documentation: <https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/>

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.1.2. OpenAIRE Research Graph: Dump of funded products

“This dataset contains the metadata records about research products (research literature, data, software, other types of research products) with funding information available in the OpenAIRE Research Graph produced on December 2022. [...] You can also search and browse this dataset (and more) in the [OpenAIRE EXPLORE portal](#) and via the [OpenAIRE API](#).”⁴

In the context of PathOS, this dataset will be used in the following case studies:

- Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP (UMINHO)
- Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence (Athena RC)
- Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications (Athena RC)

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

⁴ <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

JSON-LD

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

3.6 GB packed

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To combine with other data
- Other

The OpenAIRE research graph will be used to estimate open science impact indicators for case studies.

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

OpenAIRE

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry
- Other

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

Please refer to https://zenodo.org/record/7492313#.Y_319HZBxPY for full details.

3.1.1.9 ARE METADATA HARVESTABLE?

Yes

Please refer to https://zenodo.org/record/7492313#.Y_319HZBxPY for full details.

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

<https://zenodo.org>

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal
- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

OpenAIRE Research Graph: Dump of funded products

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Dataset will remain available from OpenAIRE.

All data is openly available, no identity will be ascertained

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

Dataset will remain available from OpenAIRE.

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CANNOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

Yes

Metadata are already available from OpenAIRE.

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

Metadata are already available from OpenAIRE.

3.2.3.4 WILL METADATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER THE DATASET / OUTPUT IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

Yes

Metadata are already available from OpenAIRE.

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.3 HAVE YOU APPLIED A STANDARD SCHEMA FOR YOUR (META)DATA?

No

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 WILL YOU PROVIDE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN?

Yes

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

No

This is provided by OpenAIRE.

3.4.5 IS PROVENANCE WELL DOCUMENTED?

Yes

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.1.3. OpenAIRE Research Graph Dump: new collected projects

“The dataset includes metadata about projects grants collected by OpenAIRE since September 2022. This dump involves:

- 640 new SNSF projects
- 1088 new HE projects
- 38462 NWO projects. Some of them are old projects collected with different OpenAIRE identifier

- 2008 new ANR projects
- 284571 new NIH projects
- 152 FWF projects
- 1 HRZZ new project
- 47089 NSF new projects
- 1 WT new project
- 8443 UKRI new projects ⁵

In the context of PathOS, this dataset will be used in the following case studies:

- Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence (ATHENA RC)
- Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications (ATHENA RC)

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

JSON-LD

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

1.7 MB packed

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To combine with other data

⁵ <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

- Other

The OpenAIRE research graph will be used to estimate open science impact indicators for case studies.

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

OpenAIRE

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry
- Other

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Projects identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

Please refer to https://zenodo.org/record/6685030#.Y_35kXZBxPZ for full details.

3.1.1.9 ARE METADATA HARVESTABLE?

Yes

Please refer to https://zenodo.org/record/6685030#.Y_35kXZBxPZ for full details.

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

<https://zenodo.org>

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

- Follows repository standards

- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention
- Supports withdrawal
- Supports back up
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Assigns PIDs
- Follows metadata standards
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Supports authentication and authorization of users
- Has data security mechanisms in place

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

OpenAIRE Research Graph Dump: new collected projects

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Dataset will remain available from OpenAIRE.

All data is openly available, no identity will be ascertained

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

Dataset will remain available from OpenAIRE.

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CANNOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

Yes

Metadata are already available from OpenAIRE.

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

Metadata are already available from OpenAIRE.

3.2.3.4 WILL METADATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER THE DATASET / OUTPUT IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

Yes

Metadata are already available from OpenAIRE.

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.3 HAVE YOU APPLIED A STANDARD SCHEMA FOR YOUR (META)DATA?

No

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 WILL YOU PROVIDE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN?

Yes

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

Yes

Output and data used for analysis will be deposited.

3.4.5 IS PROVENANCE WELL DOCUMENTED?

Yes

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.1.4. AI-Climate EU Collection of Projects and Publications enriched with FoS labels powered by SciNoBo

Collection of metadata from project documents and publications that are classified into the "artificial intelligence (AI)" and "climate change" fields of science (FoS) by the SciNoBo tool. For more information regarding the algorithm of SciNoBo, please refer to:

<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3487553.3524677>

In the context of PathOS, this dataset will be used in the following case studies:

- Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence (ATHENA RC)

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

JSON-LD

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers

- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry
- Other

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

2.3 SOFTWARE

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

No

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

1.1.5. Covid-19 EU Collection of Projects and Publications enriched with FoS labels powered by SciNoBo

Collection of metadata from project documents and publications that are classified into the "Covid-19" field of science (FoS) by the SciNoBo tool. For more information regarding the algorithm of SciNoBo, please refer to:

<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3487553.3524677>

In the context, of PathOS, this dataset will be used in the following case studies:

- Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications (ATHENA RC)

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

JSON-LD

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- The public
- Industry
- Other

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

1.1.6. The Lens (lens.org)

The Lens, formerly called Patent Lens, is an online patent and scholarly literature search facility, provided by Cambia, an Australia-based non-profit organization. The Lens serves all the patents and scholarly work in the world as a free, open and secure digital public good.

In the context of PathOS, this dataset will be used in the following case studies:

- ELIXIR's Bioinformatics Resources (ELIXIR)

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Other

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

The Lens will be used as an input dataset

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

The Lens is an agglomeration database, that takes bibliometric data from other databases (such as PubMed and Crossref) and combines them into one, deduplicated and with unified search syntax.

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

JSON Data Interchange Format

With over 20 years of development, supported by prominent philanthropic organizations, The Lens ingests, cleans, aggregates, normalizes and serves over 225+ million scholarly works, 127+ million global patent records, and more than 370+ million patent sequences, with rich metadata including the people and institutions that generate this knowledge and the linkages between them, drawn from diverse data sources. The Lens allows data exporting in JSON format.

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

225+ million scholarly works, 127+ million global patent records, and more than 370+ million patent sequences

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

To obtain information

The Lens will be used to text-mine names of ELIXIR bioinformatics resources (encompassing databases, software, tools, workflows, standards, ontologies, cloud computing, etc), as proxy for their usefulness in work leading to patent applications.

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

The Lens is the flagship project of the social enterprise Cambia (<https://cambia.org/>).

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

Nature Biotechnology (<https://www.nature.com/articles/nbt0506-474a>) called the Patent Lens "a giant leap in the right direction" for providing researchers, technology transfer offices and company executives a facile means of establishing the novelty of their offerings and the nature of their competitors' inventions.

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Other

URL

Guidance on acknowledging The Lens is at <https://support.lens.org/knowledge-base/attribution-badge/>

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

Not applicable as The Lens will be used an input dataset

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Not applicable as The Lens will be used an input dataset

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use)
- Supports mid- and long-term preservation
- Follows curation processes

3.2.1.4 ADD APPROPRIATE ARRANGEMENTS MADE WITH THE REPOSITORY(IES) WHERE THE DESCRIBED DATASET WILL BE DEPOSITED

Not applicable as The Lens will be used an input dataset

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Unknown

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

The Lens

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Not applicable as The Lens will be used as an input dataset

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Other

<https://about.lens.org/policies/>

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.1.7. FCT funding streams and projects information - SciPROJ

The FCT funding projects information - SciPROJ - is the national database that aggregates funding records (national and international) that support the science and technology activities developed in Portugal. Is based on the CERIF data model, SciPROJ provides information on 4 interconnected entities: funding, people, projects and organizations, in accordance with the adoption of the OpenAIRE data profile.

In the context of PathOS, this dataset will be used in the following case studies:

- Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP (UMINHO)

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

Reuse the content of the SciPROJ (Portuguese database with lists of funded projects by the major Portuguese funder - FCT).

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Other

Metadata records with funding information.

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

- CSV Schema
- JSON-LD

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

500 MB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

Public API available in the context of the PTCRIS initiative.

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

Research on the context of a case study analysing the compliance with the national mandate mandates the publications resulting from FCT funding to be deposited in a repository belonging to the RCAAP infrastructure.

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

2.1.2 IS THERE A DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT PROVIDED ALONG WITH THE PUBLICATION?

No

2.3 SOFTWARE

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

No

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

The described dataset has included in the data PIDs from Researchers identifiers, Organizations identifiers, Projects identifiers and others. The processed dataset will be deposited in DataRepositoriUM, so a DOI will be registered.

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

3.1.1.3 WHAT TYPE(S) OF METADATA?

Sciproj data have mainly administrative metadata, but the processed dataset will be deposited in DatRepositoriUM and via that mean have structured metadata following the standards from Dataverse software.

3.1.1.4 DO THE METADATA USE STANDARDISED VOCABULARIES?

No

3.1.1.6 ARE THE METADATA SEARCHABLE?

Yes

3.1.1.7 HOW ARE SEARCHABLE METADATA PROVIDED?

Registry/Catalogue

3.1.1.8 ARE KEYWORDS PROVIDED IN THE METADATA?

Yes

3.1.1.9 ARE METADATA HARVESTABLE?

Yes

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

DataRepositoriUM

<https://datarepositorium.uminho.pt/>

Institutional Data Repository to share, publish and manage research data generated and collected by the researchers' activity and in the research units of the University of Minho.

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.4 ADD APPROPRIATE ARRANGEMENTS MADE WITH THE REPOSITORY(IES) WHERE THE DESCRIBED DATASET WILL BE DEPOSITED

Institutional repository from the University of Minho managed by the unit involved in the project.

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes, Digital Object Identifier.

3.2.1.6 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) RESOLVE THE IDENTIFIERS TO A DIGITAL OBJECT?

DOI.

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes.

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

National database that aggregates funding records from FCT funder that support the science and technology activities developed in Portugal.

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Shared

Public API.

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CANNOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

Yes, based on Dataverse standards.

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

3.2.3.4 WILL METADATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER THE DATASET / OUTPUT IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

Yes

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

No

3.3.3 HAVE YOU APPLIED A STANDARD SCHEMA FOR YOUR (META)DATA?

Yes, we will apply descriptive metadata based on Dataverse standards, exposing the metadata compliant with Dublin core, DDI codebook, OpenAIRE, Datacite and Shecma.org.

3.3.5 WHAT IS THE METHODOLOGY FOLLOWED?

CERIF and OpenAIRE

3.3.6 WHAT COMMUNITY-ENDORSED INTEROPERABILITY BEST PRACTICES ARE FOLLOWED?

CERIF and OpenAIRE

3.3.7 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT PROVIDE QUALIFIED REFERENCES WITH OTHER OUTPUTS?

Yes

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

CC0 1.0

3.4.2 WHAT REUSABILITY AND / OR REPRODUCIBILITY METHODS ARE FOLLOWED?

Readme files

3.4.3 WILL YOU PROVIDE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN?

Yes

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

Yes

3.4.5 IS PROVENANCE WELL DOCUMENTED?

Yes

3.4.6 WHAT DOCUMENTED PROCEDURES FOR QUALITY ASSURANCE DO YOU HAVE IN PLACE?

Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1.1 WHAT WILL BE THE COST OF MAKING THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT FAIR?

Research data will be collected for reuse with minimal effort from public API collection, without many payments involved for storage and deposit in repository, as an Institutional facility is used.

Euro

Storage

Indirect cost

4.1.2 HOW WILL THIS COST BE COVERED?

Use of institution infrastructure

4.1.3 IDENTIFY THE PEOPLE WHO WILL BE RESPONSIBLE AND THEIR ROLE(S) IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT

a. Antonia Correia (orcid:0000-0002-6610-8853)

Curate and deposit.

b. Pedro Príncipe (orcid:0000-0002-8588-4196)

Curate and storage/preserve.

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

Yes

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.1.8. CNRS - OpenEditions and HAL connexion logs

HAL and Open Edition Server connexion logs cleaned and enriched by Ezparse (A tool developed by CNRS support unit INIST-UAR71) and made available in the COUNTER format on OpenEditions servers hosted by Huma-num (CNRS infrastructure).

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Other

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

The data we analysed are the connection logs to HAL's and OpenEdition's websites

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational data

The data we analysed are the connection logs to HAL's and OpenEdition's websites

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

JSON

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

10 gigabytes

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To combine with other data

The connection logs to OpenEdition's website will be aggregated with the connection logs to Hal's website to create overall statistic on usage of the two platforms

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

Those are connection logs to HAL's and OpenEdition's website. They are generated by the server, and post-processed by an automatic tool that de-noises the raw file and converts it into a CSV.

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry
- Other

This data will not be made public. It stays on OpenEdition's servers and, apart from OpenEdition, is only accessible to CIS working team during the project.

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

2.1.2 IS THERE A DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT PROVIDED ALONG WITH THE PUBLICATION?

No

2.2 DATASETS

2.2.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY PUBLISHED DATASET?

No

2.3 SOFTWARE

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

Yes

<https://pathos.cis.cnrs.fr>

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

this data will not be made public

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

this data will not be made public

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

this data will not be made public

this data will not be made public

3.2.1.4 ADD APPROPRIATE ARRANGEMENTS MADE WITH THE REPOSITORY(IES) WHERE THE DESCRIBED DATASET WILL BE DEPOSITED

this data will not be made public

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

OpenEdition and HAL connection logs

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Closed

this data will not be made public

3.2.2.3 WHAT IS THE REASON OF LIMITING ACCESS TO THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

The dataset contains personal information as per §4 of GDPR. it will be aggregated in order not to contain any directly or indirectly identifying information.

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

This data will not be made public.

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

This data will not be made public.

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CAN NOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

No

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.3.4 WILL METADATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER THE DATASET / OUTPUT IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

No

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

No

3.3.3 HAVE YOU APPLIED A STANDARD SCHEMA FOR YOUR (META)DATA?

No

3.3.4 WILL YOU PROVIDE A MAPPING TO MORE COMMONLY USED ONTOLOGIES?

No

3.3.7 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT PROVIDE QUALIFIED REFERENCES WITH OTHER OUTPUTS?

No

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.2 WHAT REUSABILITY AND / OR REPRODUCIBILITY METHODS ARE FOLLOWED?

Codebooks

3.4.3 WILL YOU PROVIDE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN?

No

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

No

3.4.5 IS PROVENANCE WELL DOCUMENTED?

Yes

3.4.6 WHAT DOCUMENTED PROCEDURES FOR QUALITY ASSURANCE DO YOU HAVE IN PLACE?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

Data conforms to COUNTER5 standards <https://cop5.projectcounter.org/en/5.0.2/03-specifications/index.html>

4.1 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1.1 WHAT WILL BE THE COST OF MAKING THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT FAIR?

This data will not be made public.

US Dollar

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

- Other

This data will not be made public.

All costs related to data management are supported by OpenEdition and Huma-Num, french international digital infrastructure for human and social sciences <https://www.huma-num.fr/quest-ce-que-l-ir-huma-num/>

4.1.2 HOW WILL THIS COST BE COVERED?

- Use of national infrastructure
- Use of institution infrastructure

All costs related to data management are supported by OpenEdition and Huma-Num, french international digital infrastructure for human and social sciences <https://www.huma-num.fr/quest-ce-que-l-ir-huma-num/>

4.1.3 IDENTIFY THE PEOPLE WHO WILL BE RESPONSIBLE AND THEIR ROLE(S) IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT

Melanie Dulong de Rosnay (0000-0002-0297-7603)

5.1 DATA SECURITY

5.1.1 WHAT SECURITY MEASURES ARE FOLLOWED?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

5.1.2 WHAT CONDITIONS DO THE SECURITY MEASURES MEET?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data transmission
- Data sharing

5.1.3 HOW WILL YOU PRESERVE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE LONG TERM?

This data will not be made public.

As they are connexion logs, RGPD compliance rules forces OpenEdition's system administrators to delete them after a legal period of time.

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

no

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

Yes

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

Yes

7.1.2 DOCUMENTATION OF OTHER PROCEDURES

We also use CNRS data treatment declaration tool called Revcil. All our data treatments are validated and supervised by CNRS's data protection officer, which also supervises OpenEdition's overall data RGPD compliance, as OpenEdition is also a CNRS unit.

1.1.9. EP full-text data 2024

A bulk data collection including the full text in machine-readable format of all patent applications and granted patent specifications published by the EPO since it was set up in 1978. It's possible to search the complete EP full-text collection using our own search interface, in-house database or search engine.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

Database

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

XML ST36 and PDF/A

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

4 GB (zipped)

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

To obtain information

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

European Patent Office

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education
- Industry

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

1.1.10. EuropePMC

Using EuropePMC (an ELIXIR Core Data Resource providing comprehensive access to life sciences literature from trusted sources), we use a range of search terms on funding linked to ELIXIR, as well as on its achievements through its operation and projects, to identify ELIXIR-supported publications.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

1.1.11. Research Organization Registry (ROR.org)

The Research Organization Registry (ROR) is a global, community-led registry of open, unique, and persistent identifiers for every research organization in the world. ROR identifiers are designed to connect research outputs with their institutional affiliations, making it possible to track and analyze the contributions of organizations to the scholarly record in a standardized, machine-actionable way. ROR fills a critical gap in the scholarly infrastructure by providing open identifiers and metadata for more than 106,000 research organizations worldwide, spanning universities, research institutes, funding bodies, and facilities. ROR records include canonical names, acronyms, location details, and links to external identifiers such as GRID, ISNI, Wikidata, and Crossref Funder Registry. ROR IDs are openly available via an API and downloadable dataset, enabling broad adoption across repositories, publishers, funders, and metadata aggregators.

In the context of PathOS, ROR has been used in the following case studies:

- Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications (Athena RC)
- Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence (Athena RC)
- ELIXIR's Bioinformatics Resources (ELIXIR)
- Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP (UMIHNO)

Learn more at <https://ror.org>.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Other

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

ROR is an existing, community-maintained registry. In PathOS, we reuse ROR data to support organizational disambiguation and institutional-level analysis.

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Reference or canonical

ROR.org is a canonical registry of persistent identifiers and metadata for research organizations, maintained as an authoritative reference dataset for affiliation disambiguation and linking research outputs.

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

JSON, downloadable dumps

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

61MB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To combine with other data

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

Researchers

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Organizations identifiers

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

ROR provides rich metadata (name, aliases, acronyms, country, external links, etc.), openly available via API and downloadable JSON dumps.

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/records/16950727>

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

ROR Data

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

Yes

ROR is a global, sustainable community infrastructure, designed for long-term reuse beyond project duration.

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

no

ROR contains no sensitive or restricted data; all records are institutional metadata.

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

No

7 OTHER ISSUES

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

Yes

7.1.2 DOCUMENTATION OF OTHER PROCEDURES

ROR follows community best practices in open metadata, version control, and governance through its open issue tracker and update process.

1.1.12. CORD-19 Open Research Dataset

The COVID-19 dataset contains academic journal articles relating to a variety of coronaviruses and related viral infections, not only COVID-19, sourced from PubMed Central (PMC), PubMed, the World Health Organization (WHO), bioRxiv, medRxiv, and arXiv.

Within the Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications case study, COVID-19 is used as a dataset to identify COVID-19 related publications.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

To identify COVID-19 related publications for the COVID-19 case study.

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

JSON-formatted metadata, structured full-text article parses (e.g., S2ORC JSON), and CSV metadata files

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

18.7 GB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

The dataset was assembled by the Allen Institute for AI in partnership with OSTP, NLM, CZI, Microsoft Research, Georgetown CSET, and others, drawing on multiple publication sources and processed via Semantic Scholar pipelines.

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes (inherited from CORD-19).

3.1.1.4 DO THE METADATA USE STANDARDISED VOCABULARIES?

Yes

3.1.1.6 ARE THE METADATA SEARCHABLE?

Yes

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Antibody Registry

TIB

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

The CORD-19 dataset contains academic journal articles relating to a variety of coronaviruses and related viral infections, not only COVID-19, sourced from PubMed Central (PMC), PubMed, the World Health Organization (WHO), bioRxiv, medRxiv, and arXiv.

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

No

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

Yes

Dataset remains openly available to all researchers for future reuse.

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

no

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

No

7 OTHER ISSUES

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

Yes

7.1.2 DOCUMENTATION OF OTHER PROCEDURES

CORD-19 includes version control, changelog documentation, and metadata harmonization pipelines

1.1.13. Semantic Scholar Academic Graph

Semantic Scholar provides a large-scale, AI-enhanced corpus of scholarly metadata, including bibliographic information, citation links, references, and influential-citation metrics derived from machine-learning models. In the context of the PathOS project, the dataset is reused in the following case studies:

- Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence (Athena RC)

- Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications (Athena RC)
- ELIXIR's Bioinformatics Resources (ELIXIR)
- Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP (UMIHNO)

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

Semantic Scholar is reused as an external resource; no new data are generated within PathOS.

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

JSON, CSV, and API-delivered structured metadata

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

>250GB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

Semantic Scholar, developed and maintained by the Allen Institute for AI (AI2).

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

- Data identifiers
- Researchers identifiers
- Organizations identifiers

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

3.1.1.4 DO THE METADATA USE STANDARDISED VOCABULARIES?

Yes

3.1.1.6 ARE THE METADATA SEARCHABLE?

Yes

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Semantic Scholar (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/>)

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Semantic Scholar Academic Graph

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

3.2.2.6 PLEASE PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT THE METHOD(S) NEEDED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT.

Semantic Scholar API or downloadable data dumps.

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Access will continue through the Semantic Scholar API and public data dumps after the end of PathOS.

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

Indefinitely, as long as AI2 maintains Semantic Scholar.

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CAN NOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

Yes

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

Yes

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

no

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

No

7 OTHER ISSUES

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.1.14. PubMed

PubMed is a large biomedical and life sciences database maintained by the U.S. National Library of Medicine (NLM). It indexes peer-reviewed literature. In the context of the PathOS project, PubMed Data is reused to identify, extract, and analyse COVID-19-related scholarly publications for the Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications case study. The reuse enables tracking of open science practices, such as artefact referencing and artefact reuse and supports the assessment of downstream impact in academic, economic, and societal domains.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

This dataset is reused to identify clinical guideline and clinical trial related articles for the COVID-19 case study. Original data are curated and maintained by PubMed.

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

This dataset consists of bibliographic metadata (titles, abstracts, identifiers, affiliations, subject terms) curated and maintained by PubMed.

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

XML

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

~60GB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

U.S. National Library of Medicine (NLM), National Institutes of Health (NIH), Bethesda, USA.

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Data identifiers

PMID (PubMed ID)

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

Metadata are provided by PubMed and retained during reuse; project-specific enrichments are documented separately.

3.1.1.4 DO THE METADATA USE STANDARDISED VOCABULARIES?

Yes

3.1.1.6 ARE THE METADATA SEARCHABLE?

Yes

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

PubMed

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes

3.2.1.6 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) RESOLVE THE IDENTIFIERS TO A DIGITAL OBJECT?

Yes, PubMed assigns PMIDs; many records also include DOIs.

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

PubMed Data

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

3.2.2.6 PLEASE PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT THE METHOD(S) NEEDED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT.

Accessible via PubMed's web interface, API, and bulk XML downloads.

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Through the PubMed platform and APIs; continued access is maintained by NLM.

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

Indefinitely, as maintained by PubMed.

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CAN NOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

Yes

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

Yes, reuse is guaranteed through PubMed's permanent access.

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

no

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

No

7 OTHER ISSUES

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.1.15. SciNoBo Toolkit

The SciNoBo Toolkit is an open, modular platform for science-of-science analytics, developed by ILSP/Athena RC. It provides automated bibliometric classification, topic modelling, and impact measurement through a suite of services and APIs. Its functionalities support fine-grained analysis of scholarly outputs, making it a valuable resource for Open Science assessments.

In the context of PathOS, the SciNoBo toolkit is reused as an analytical instrument in several case studies, including :

- Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence (Athena RC)
- Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications (Athena RC)
- ELIXIR´ s Bioinformatics Resources (ELIXIR)
- Effects of Data Repositories on Data Usage (ULEI)
- ELIXIR´ s Bioinformatics Resources (ELIXIR)
- Portuguese Repository Infrastructure RCAAP (UMIHNO)

In these contexts, different modules of SciNoBo are applied:

- Field of Science Classifier → assigns publications to disciplinary categories, enabling topic clustering and thematic persistence analysis.
- Citation Analysis → provides citation counts, field-weighted citation impact, and influential-citation signals.

- Research Artefact Analysis & Citance Analysis → identifies datasets or software referenced in publications and traces their explicit reuse in later works.
- Science–Industry Collaboration module → detects co-authorship links between academic and industry-affiliated researchers.
- Clinical Trials and Guidelines Uptake module → maps scientific outputs into medical practice through citations in clinical trials and health guidelines.

These services ensure comparability across case studies and reduce duplication of effort by harmonising metrics such as topic persistence, academic impact, and societal or economic uptake.

Access to the toolkit: <https://scinobo.ilsp.gr/toolkit>

TOOL DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Software

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

Developed by the Institute for Language and Speech Processing (ILSP) at Athena RC.

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

2 LINKS BETWEEN OUTPUTS

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

a. Yes

[SCINOBO: a novel system classifying scholarly communication in a dynamically constructed hierarchical Field-of-Science taxonomy](#)

b. Yes

[SciNoBo: A Hierarchical Multi-Label Classifier of Scientific Publications](#)

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

GitHub

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

SciNoBo Toolkit

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Continues to be maintained by Athena RC beyond PathOS.

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

Indefinite → Maintained as institutional infrastructure.

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

no

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

No

1.1.16. Gender Classification Model

The Gender-Classification model (Hugging Face Hub ID: padmajabfrl/Gender-Classification, DOI: 10.57967/hf/4569) is a fine-tuned version of distilbert-base-uncased. It applies transformer-based text classification to infer likely gender based on given names or short text inputs.

In the PathOS project, this model is reused to support gender-signal inference in the Impact of Open Access Routes on Topic Persistence Case Study. It is applied to author names extracted from publication metadata to approximate the gender composition of research teams.

TOOL DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Models

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

It is reused to support gender-signal inference in the Emerging Topics Case Study. It is applied to author names extracted from publication metadata to approximate the gender composition of research teams.

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

PyTorch model files (binary weights), config files in JSON, model card in Markdown.

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

~250 MB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To make informed decisions
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

Hugging Face Hub (padmajabfrl/Gender-Classification)

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- The public

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

DOI

10.57967/hf/4569

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Hugging Face Hub

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Gender Classification Model

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

Apache Software License 2.0

1.1.17. DataStet Toolkit

The DataStet toolkit (<https://github.com/kermitt2/datastet>) is an open-source machine learning and natural language processing (NLP) system designed to identify mentions of datasets in scientific literature, including both explicitly named datasets and implicit data references within text. It also classifies the context of dataset mentions as used, created, or shared in the underlying research.

In the PathOS project, DataStet is reused to support the "Effects of Data Repositories on Data Usage" case study, where it detects dataset creation and reuse signals in scientific publications.

TOOL DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Software

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions

1.1.9 To WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

GitHub

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

DataStet Toolkit

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

Apache Software License 2.0

3.4.2 WHAT REUSABILITY AND / OR REPRODUCIBILITY METHODS ARE FOLLOWED?

Readme files

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

no

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

No

1.1.18. Data Citation Corpus Data File

Data file for the fourth release of the Data Citation Corpus, produced by DataCite and Make Data Count as part of an ongoing grant project funded by the Wellcome Trust. [Read more about the project.](#)

The data file includes 10,697,745 data citation records (of which 9,682,257 represent unique dataset-publication pairs) in JSON and CSV formats. The JSON file is the version of record.

Data is provided in batches of approximately 1 million records each. The publication date and batch number are included in the file name, ex: 2025-08-15-data-citation-corpus-01-v4.1.json.

The data citations in the file originate from the following sources:

- DataCite Event Data
- Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (CZI) Science Knowledge Graph
- Aligning Science Across Parkinson's (ASAP)
- Europe PMC

Each data citation record is comprised of:

- A pair of identifiers: An identifier for the dataset (a DOI or an accession number) and the DOI of the publication (journal article or preprint) in which the dataset is cited
- Metadata for the cited dataset and for the citing publication

Additional documentation about the citations and metadata in the file is available on the [Make Data Count website](#).

Notes on v4.1:

Version 4.1 of the Data Citation Corpus is a minor update to v4.0 that corrects (1) an error that occurred when a portion of DOI-DOI citations originating from Europe PMC were attributed to the wrong repository, and (2) a small number of DOI formatting errors in the "publication" field.

Notes on v4.0:

The fourth release of the Data Citation Corpus data file adds new citations from the following sources:

- 5.2 million data citations from [Europe PMC](#) identified as "eupmc" in the source field. Ingest of these citations was performed 9 July 2025.

- 139,647 data citations from DataCite Event Data for the period 1 January 2025 through 30 June 2025.

This release also includes the following new metadata enhancements:

- Affiliation information for cited data from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) repository, reconciled to Research Organization Registry (ROR) IDs where possible.
- Reconciliation of organization and funders names with the Research Organization Registry (ROR) for new citations from Event Data.
- Application of Field of Science subject terms to citation records originating from Europe PMC, based on disciplinary area of data repository.

Additional details about the above changes, including scripts used to perform the above tasks, are available in [GitHub](#).

Additional enhancements to the corpus are ongoing and will be addressed in the course of subsequent releases. Users are invited to submit feedback via [GitHub](#). For general questions, email info@makedatacount.org.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

2025-08-15-data-citation-corpus-v4.1-json.zip

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

DOI

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Data Citation Corpus Data File

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

1.1.19. DataCite Public Data File.

Contains metadata records in JSON format for all 52,863,283 DataCite DOIs in Findable state that were registered up to the end of 2023.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

DataCite

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

DataCite Public Data File. Contains metadata records in JSON format for all 52,863,283 DataCite DOIs in Findable state that were registered up to the end of 2023.

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

1.1.20. OpenAlex

OpenAlex is an open, comprehensive index of scholarly papers, citations, authors, institutions, and journals.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

GZIP compressed JSON lines

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

~250GB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

<https://docs.openalex.org/>

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers
- Education
- The public

2 LINKS BETWEEN OUTPUTS

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

Yes

OpenAlex: A fully-open index of scholarly works, authors, venues, institutions, and concepts

2.1.2 IS THERE A DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT PROVIDED ALONG WITH THE PUBLICATION?

Yes

2.3 SOFTWARE

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

No

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

1.1.21. Eurostat NACE Rev. 2.1

The 'statistical classification of economic activities' in the European Community, abbreviated as NACE, is the classification of economic activities in the European Union (EU). The term NACE is derived from the French title: Nomenclature statistique des activités économiques dans la Communauté européenne. Various NACE versions have been developed since 1970.

The newest version is NACE revision 2 update 1 (NACE Rev. 2.1), which is to be used for European statistics from 2025 onwards. It was adopted by the European Commission in October 2022.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Models

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Reference or canonical

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

rdf, tsv, csv

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

~1,5 mo

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

European Union

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public

2 LINKS BETWEEN OUTPUTS

2.2 DATASETS

2.2.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY PUBLISHED DATASET?

Yes

2.3 SOFTWARE

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/records/17471200>

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.5 PLEASE PROVIDE URL/DESCRIPTION OF USED VOCABULARIES

https://showvoc.op.europa.eu/#/datasets/ESTAT_Statistical_Classification_of_Economic_Activities_in_the_European_Community_Rev._2.1._%28NACE_2.1%29/data

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

NACE Rev 2.1

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

1.1.22. IPinfo's Academic Research Program

IPinfo is a delivering comprehensive and precise IP data API run by DB LLC, a Delaware corporation. A partial subset of their data is made available for free for academic purposes. It contains following fields :

IP to Company : - start_ip, end_ip, name, domain, type, asn, as_name, as_domain, as_type, country

IP to Geolocation : - start_ip, end_ip, city, region, country, lat, lng, postal, timezone

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

API response in json format

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To combine with other data

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

IPinfo's services "combines ground truth data with data from global Probe Network (<https://ipinfo.io/probe-network>) to create a detailed, real-time profile of every IP address". <https://ipinfo.io/about>

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy

- The public
- Industry
- Other

The data/services provided is for use only by the approved individuals for the express purpose of the agreed-upon academic research. Any purpose or use not directly related to academic research or education is strictly prohibited - for the avoidance of doubt any direct or indirect commercial purpose or use is prohibited.

2 LINKS BETWEEN OUTPUTS

2.3 SOFTWARE

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

Yes

<https://zenodo.org/records/17471200>

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

5 SECURITY

5.1 DATA SECURITY

5.1.1 WHAT SECURITY MEASURES ARE FOLLOWED?

The information we retrieve from IPinfo's API about IP addresses remains secret, stored on a SSH access restricted virtual machine. IPinfo helps us finding the domain name which corresponds to IP ranges. We then classify those domain names into NACE categories, and only publish statistics aggregated by NACE category.

1.1.23. ElasticSearch and Kibana

OpenEdition and HAL logs are augmented with information about the articles (scientific domain) and the ip addresses of the user accessing the articles (socio-economical sector).

The logs are massive (453 million consultation events) and in order to be explored they need to be indexed on a powerful search engine, Elasticsearch, running on a virtual machine, which has a dedicated user-friendly interface, Kibana, allowing for easy aggregations, simple exploratory graphs and statistics.

Elasticsearch is an open source, distributed search and analytics engine built for speed, scale, and AI applications. As a retrieval platform, it stores structured, unstructured, and vector data in real time — delivering fast hybrid and vector search, powering observability and security analytics, and enabling AI-driven applications with high performance, accuracy, and relevance.

TOOL DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Software

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

Re-used

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

.exe (Windows) or .tar.gz

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

500mo

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To share information
- To make informed decisions

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry
- Other

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

<https://gitlab.huma-num.fr/path-os/ouestware>

This repository contains all the docker config files we used to set up an Elastic Search + Kibana instance on our servers in order to process the data

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

5 SECURITY

5.1 DATA SECURITY

5.1.1 WHAT SECURITY MEASURES ARE FOLLOWED?

SSH restricted acces to the VM, once in VM, Kibana+ElasticSearch only accessible through localhost on specific ports

1.2. Output Datasets and Tools

1.2.1. All Output Datasets

This section of the Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the procedures and metadata standards we will employ to ensure the datasets created during the project adhere to the principles of FAIRness—making them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. While each project partner retains their data on their own premises, adhering to their internal data management protocols, we have established a unified approach for handling the datasets generated within the scope of the project. The rules and guidelines detailed in this entry are designed to harmonize our efforts, ensuring that all project-generated datasets meet the current standards of data stewardship. This approach not only facilitates compliance with FAIR principles but also enhances the datasets' utility and longevity, enabling broader access and collaboration within the research community.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Various types of output datasets are expected.

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

In PathOS, all produced datasets, whether open or closed, will be accompanied by detailed metadata to ensure they meet FAIR principles. Closed datasets will be catalogued in Zenodo as separate sources and our Data Management Plan (DMP), with metadata available under a CC-0 license. Open datasets will be deposited in Zenodo with a CC-BY license if they are small in size, and we are considering alternative sharing methods, like APIs, for larger datasets. We use the OpenAIRE Guidelines metadata schema, which is aligned with EOSC the EOSC interoperability framework, based on the Dublin Core and aligned with Zenodo as well (<https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/index.html>).

3.1.1.4 DO THE METADATA USE STANDARDISED VOCABULARIES?

Yes

3.1.1.5 PLEASE PROVIDE URL/DESCRIPTION OF USED VOCABULARIES

<https://developers.zenodo.org/?python#representation>.

3.1.1.6 ARE THE METADATA SEARCHABLE?

Yes

3.1.1.7 HOW ARE SEARCHABLE METADATA PROVIDED?

Registry/Catalogue

3.1.1.8 ARE KEYWORDS PROVIDED IN THE METADATA?

Yes

3.1.1.9 ARE METADATA HARVESTABLE?

Yes

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Open datasets will be deposited in Zenodo

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CAN NOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

Yes

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

3.3.3 HAVE YOU APPLIED A STANDARD SCHEMA FOR YOUR (META)DATA?

Yes

1.2.2. Collaborations extracted from RCAAP based on the citation and network analysis

Dataset with the results of the Citation and network analysis to derive collaborations in specific domains between academia and industry using the Portuguese network of repositories (RCAAP) content harvested in OpenAIRE graph and including the Open Citations data included in the graph.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

Generating a new dataset based on datasets consider in the PATHOS DMP.

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

CSV Schema

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

1.2.3. Case study focus group data

This dataset is constituted by video recordings of online focus groups held with stakeholders to provide feedback on and insights for the development of the project's case studies, impact pathways, and indicators. This dataset will be used internally to facilitate this work and will not be shared openly to protect the privacy of participants.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

These data are video recordings of online focus groups conducted throughout the PathOS project.

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

Digital Video

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

Unknown at this time

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To keep on record
- To make informed decisions

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

The data will be generated through a series of focus group discussions, including a range of participants, across seven case studies and over the lifespan of the PathOS project.

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

Researchers

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

2.3 SOFTWARE

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

No

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

None

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

PathOS case study focus group data

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Closed

The dataset is closed to protect the privacy of those who participate in the focus groups.

3.2.2.3 WHAT IS THE REASON OF LIMITING ACCESS TO THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

Within the focus groups participants may critique aspects of products or processes that they are directly involved with through employment and therefore sharing the dataset openly would reduce their willingness to participate and/or limit what they are willing to share in the focus groups, thus hampering the aims of the research.

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

The data from each case will be available only to the case team in their secured cloud storage environment. Raw data will not be shared outside of each case team (e.g., not with the entire project consortium). Raw data will be preserved for up to three years after the conclusion of the project.

Case team members are required to enter private and confidential login details to access their cloud-based storage systems.

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CANNOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

No

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

No

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

No

4.1 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1.1 WHAT WILL BE THE COST OF MAKING THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT FAIR?

0

Euro

Storage

4.1.2 HOW WILL THIS COST BE COVERED?

Other

5.1 DATA SECURITY

5.1.1 WHAT SECURITY MEASURES ARE FOLLOWED?

Passwords

Data are stored in password-protected, cloud-storage environments (e.g., Microsoft Teams).

5.1.2 WHAT CONDITIONS DO THE SECURITY MEASURES MEET?

Data storage

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

yes

Participants may share critiques of products or processes that they are involved with through their employment, and therefore could experience the risk of institutional repercussions if the data were openly shared.

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

Yes

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

Yes

6.1.4 WHAT ARE THE METHODS USED FOR PROCESSING AND ACCESSING SENSITIVE/PERSONAL INFORMATION?

- Anonymising data where necessary
- Privacy constraints and applicable ethical norms
- Data accompanied by informed consent statements

Yes

Members of case study teams alone will be able to access raw data from their focus groups. Information created and shared based on these data, including notes, cross-case data synthesis, project meetings, documents and reports will not contain any personally identifiable information. Results of focus groups will be aggregated and fully anonymized when shared outside of the case team.

Personal information, including participants' first and last names, affiliations, positions, gender and email addresses are recorded in a project-internal spreadsheet that is secured in a password-protected Microsoft Teams environment that is only accessible to project consortium members.

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.2.4. Mentions of ELIXIR resource names in patent applications (via lens.org)

Using The Lens (lens.org), a patent and scholarly literature search facility, we regularly text-mine names of ELIXIR resources in patent applications. We use this as proxy of their usefulness to bioinformaticians of all sectors (academic, industry), and across the globe. We are working to expand our searches to cover all ELIXIR resources (>400), as well as being able to visualise patent applications by main sectors.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Other

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

Our approach is loosely inspired from earlier ELIXIR work (<https://f1000research.com/articles/5-160/v1>), but less computationally intensive, yet lightweight and repeatable so as to operationalise it as an indicator.

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

The dataset is a list of patent applications in which ELIXIR resources (<https://elixir-europe.org/services>) are mentioned by name. The Lens is text-mined once a week using a number of search terms relating to ELIXIR resource names. Patent applications containing one or more of these search terms are then added to a spreadsheet, with the following fields being extracted from The Lens:

- jurisdiction where the patent application was filed
- lens.org unique ID
- publication date
- application number and date
- title, abstract
- applicant names (institutions)
- URL in lens.org
- IPCR classifications

Manual curation of the returned patent applications is then carried out, so as to exclude false positives. The curated list feeds visualisations at <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/patents>.

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

OpenDocument Spreadsheet

The dataset is currently maintained as a Google spreadsheet - the format allows for collaborative manual curation to be carried out, as well as direct feeding of online visualisations. It is anticipated that this will remain the format for as long as the indicator will be maintained. A download option may be added to the visualisation URL once the exercise has become less qualitative.

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

20MB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions

In the context of the PathOS project, the dataset will inform the work of the Focus Group convened as part of the bioinformatics case study, as well as the cost-benefit analysis.

See <https://pathos-project.eu/how-open-bioinformatics-resources-foster-innovation-in-industry-a-short-interview> for a summary.

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

The Lens (lens.org)

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Decision makers
- Other

This dataset is part of a broader body of work carried out by ELIXIR to demonstrate its public value to funders and decision-makers.

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

None

This feature will be implemented once the dataset is deemed suitable (i.e. sufficiently robust) for sharing.

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

Metadata will be produced once the dataset is deemed suitable (i.e. sufficiently robust) for sharing.

3.1.1.4 DO THE METADATA USE STANDARDISED VOCABULARIES?

No

3.1.1.6 ARE THE METADATA SEARCHABLE?

No

3.1.1.8 ARE KEYWORDS PROVIDED IN THE METADATA?

No

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/patents>, through a download functionality

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Mentions of ELIXIR resource names in patent applications (using lens.org)

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Shared

3.2.2.3 WHAT IS THE REASON OF LIMITING ACCESS TO THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

The dataset will be openly accessible when deemed suitable (i.e., sufficiently robust).

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/patents>, through a download functionality

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CANNOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

Yes

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/patents>, through a download functionality

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

CC0 1.0

4.1 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1.3 IDENTIFY THE PEOPLE WHO WILL BE RESPONSIBLE AND THEIR ROLE(S) IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT

Corinne Martin (orcid:0000-0002-5428-2766)

1.2.5. Mentions of ELIXIR-supported publications in

EuropePMC

Using EuropePMC (an ELIXIR Core Data Resource providing comprehensive access to life sciences literature from trusted sources), we use a range of search terms on funding linked to ELIXIR, as well as on its achievements through its operation and projects, to identify ELIXIR-supported publications.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Other

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

The dataset is a list of publications that have received financial support (e.g. grant funding, event sponsorship) or other support (e.g. in-kind contribution, use of the infrastructure and its many services) linked to ELIXIR (<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/publications/how-acknowledge>). Manual curation of monthly searches is carried out, so as to exclude false positives. The curated list feeds visualisations at <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/publications>.

Note: the dataset excludes publications that make use of ELIXIR resources, as this is monitored through other processes.

ELIXIR partners collaborate to publish research articles (peer-reviewed and preprints) on the development and operation of bioinformatics resources encompassing databases, tools, cloud computing, standards and training. These publications highlight ELIXIR's scientific legacy as a research infrastructure, and their citations by others (in the open literature) demonstrate the extent of ELIXIR's contribution and appreciation by others.

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

The dataset is currently maintained as a Google spreadsheet - the format allows for collaborative manual curation to be carried out, as well as direct feeding of online visualisations. It is anticipated that this will remain the format for as long as the indicator will be maintained. A download option may be added to the visualisation URL once the exercise has become less qualitative.

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

20MB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To share information
- To make informed decisions

In the context of the PathOS project, the dataset will inform the work of the Focus Group convened as part of the bioinformatics case study, as well as the cost-benefit analysis. See <https://pathos-project.eu/how-open-bioinformatics-resources-foster-innovation-in-industry-a-short-interview> for a summary.

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

EuropePMC

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Decision makers
- Other

This dataset is part of a broader body of work carried out by ELIXIR to demonstrate its public value to funders and decision-makers.

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

2.2 DATASETS

2.2.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY PUBLISHED DATASET?

No

2.3 SOFTWARE

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

No

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

None

URL

This feature will be implemented once the dataset is deemed suitable (i.e. sufficiently robust) for sharing.

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

3.1.1.3 WHAT TYPE(S) OF METADATA?

Metadata will be produced once the dataset is deemed suitable (i.e. sufficiently robust) for sharing.

3.1.1.4 DO THE METADATA USE STANDARDISED VOCABULARIES?

No

3.1.1.6 ARE THE METADATA SEARCHABLE?

No

3.1.1.8 ARE KEYWORDS PROVIDED IN THE METADATA?

No

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Not applicable as EuropePMC will be used as an input dataset

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Unknown

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Mentions of ELIXIR-supported publications in EuropePMC

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Shared

3.2.2.3 WHAT IS THE REASON OF LIMITING ACCESS TO THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

The dataset will be openly accessible when deemed suitable (i.e. sufficiently robust).

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/publications>, through a download functionality

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

<https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/impact/publications>, through a download functionality

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

Yes

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

CC0 1.0

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.2.6. Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications

Case Study Results and Indicators

This dataset contains the results and indicators produced in the PathOS COVID-19 case study, which investigates how Open Science practices such as artifact referencing (traceability) and artifact reuse (reusability) affect downstream academic, societal, and economic impact in COVID-19 research.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

XLSX and PNG files

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

~80MB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information
- To share information

To capture, harmonise and share empirical results and indicators used in the COVID-19 case study, supporting transparency, reproducibility, and future reuse.

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

Derived from large-scale bibliometric and metadata collections, harmonised within the PathOS project methodology.

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Impact of Artefact Reuse in COVID-19 Publications Case Study Results and Indicators Dataset

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Accessible through Zenodo with DOI-based referencing

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

Accessible through Zenodo with DOI-based referencing

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

No

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.2 WHAT REUSABILITY AND / OR REPRODUCIBILITY METHODS ARE FOLLOWED?

Readme files

3.4.3 WILL YOU PROVIDE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN?

Yes

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

Yes

3.4.5 IS PROVENANCE WELL DOCUMENTED?

Yes

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

No

7 OTHER ISSUES

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.2.7. Impact of Open Access Colors on Topic Persistence

Case Study Results and Indicators

This dataset is created as part of the PathOS Emerging Topics case study. It contains results and indicators derived from an analysis of Open Access routes (Green OA and Published OA) and their effects on the persistence of AI-for-Climate research topics. The dataset consolidates bibliometric, economic, and equity-related indicators, including citation metrics, topic-persistence scores, gender authorship signals, patent linkages, and collaboration data.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Observational

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

XLSX and PNG files

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

~16MB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

- To obtain information

- To share information

To capture, harmonise, and openly share the results and indicators from the Emerging Topics case study, ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and reuse in Open Science policy analysis.

1.1.8 WHAT IS ITS ORIGIN / PROVENANCE?

Derived from bibliometric and metadata sources including OpenAIRE, Semantic Scholar, PATSTAT, and SciNoBo taxonomy, processed and harmonised according to PathOS methodology.

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Industry

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Data identifiers

DOI

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Impact of Open Access Colors on Topic Persistence Case Study Results and Indicators Dataset

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Accessible through Zenodo with DOI-based referencing

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

Accessible through Zenodo with DOI-based referencing

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

No

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.3 WILL YOU PROVIDE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN?

Yes

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

Yes

3.4.5 IS PROVENANCE WELL DOCUMENTED?

Yes

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

no

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

No

7 OTHER ISSUES

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.2.8. Bioinformatics job vacancies analysis

The text of job vacancies published in ELIXIR vacancy portal was extracted and analysed for 15 skills identified as critical for the bioinformatics sector. Vacancies were categorised as either industry or academic based on the recruiting organisation.

The raw data and the analysis for the PathOS WP3 Case study can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17184821>.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

1.2.9. Automated Nace Domain Classifier

In order to be able to say what domain names belong to what sector of activity, we use a node.js script that queries a Llama 3.3 API run by Huma-Num (<https://www.huma-num.fr/>) to generate descriptive keywords for each domain, and then sends a second request to classify them into NACE level-1 economic activity sectors.

Llama 3.3 is a text-only 70B instruction-tuned model that provides enhanced performance relative to Llama 3.1 70B—and relative to Llama 3.2 90B when used for text-only applications. Moreover, for some applications, Llama 3.3 70B approaches the performance of Llama 3.1 405B.

TOOL DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Software

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

automated-nace-classifier-automated-nace-classifier.tar

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

DOI

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Repository hosted by Zenodo

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Automated Nace Domain Classifier

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

1.2.10. French Open Science Log Explorer

The Log Explorer has been developed by the CNRS Center for Internet & Society and the PathOS project and in close collaboration with HAL and OpenEdition, and with the support of IPInfo. It means to facilitate the investigation of the very first step in the impact pathway of Open Science (OS). This first step corresponds, of course, to the access of OS resources: the fact that these resources are consulted by users on the websites and portals that make them publicly available.

To chase these weak and initial signs of impact, the Log Explorer allows exploring one year of the logs recorded by the platforms HAL and OpenEdition journals (between January and December 2023 OpenEdition journals and between September 2023 et August 2024 pour HAL). Read the methods page to know more about how the LogExplorer works.

TOOL DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Software

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

<https://pathos.cis.cnrs.fr/>

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

It's a website. And the source code is written in Typescript

2 LINKS BETWEEN OUTPUTS

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

<https://gitlab.huma-num.fr/path-os/ouestware>

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

1.2.11. Data from Scoping Review on Impact of Open

Science

These datasets originate from the scoping review on the academic, economic, and societal impact of Open Science. They include bibliographic information, as well as data on the search, screening, and data extraction processes. A first set of results is presented in PathOS deliverable D1.2, with further extended and revised data building the foundation for peer-reviewed publications.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

Bibliographic data compiled through search processes and subjected to screening and extraction procedures

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

Mainly csv files

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

200MB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

To obtain information

1.1.9 To WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers
- Education
- Economy
- The public
- Industry

2 LINKS BETWEEN OUTPUTS

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

a. Yes

[The societal impact of Open Science: a scoping review](#)

Royal Society Open Science

ZENODO

b. Yes

[The academic impact of Open Science: a scoping review](#)

Royal Society Open Science

ZENODO

2.1.2 IS THERE A DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT PROVIDED ALONG WITH THE PUBLICATION?

Yes

2.3 SOFTWARE

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

Yes

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7969951>,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14674544>,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10559446>,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14892767>

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

3.1.1.6 ARE THE METADATA SEARCHABLE?

Yes

3.1.1.8 ARE KEYWORDS PROVIDED IN THE METADATA?

No

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

ZENODO

<https://zenodo.org/records/7969951>, <https://zenodo.org/records/14674544>,
<https://zenodo.org/records/10559446>, <https://zenodo.org/records/14892767>

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Data are and will be publicly available through a trusted repository (ZENODO).

Anyone can access.

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

Data will remain accessible for the lifetime of the repository (at least 20 years).

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.2 WHAT REUSABILITY AND / OR REPRODUCIBILITY METHODS ARE FOLLOWED?

- Readme files
- Data cleaning
- Variable definitions

3.4.3 WILL YOU PROVIDE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN?

Yes

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

Yes

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

no

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

No

7 OTHER ISSUES

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

1.2.12. Dataset – UniProt and RCAAP CBA Case Studies (PathOS Project)

This dataset contains the data underlying the Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) case studies. It includes:

- Anonymised results from the user survey conducted to estimate benefits in the UniProt and RCAAP case studies.
- Overview of the annual costs and benefits of the UniProt and RCAAP resources
- Summary tables of the CBA results consistent with the findings presented in the related case studies and factsheets.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Primary (survey data) and secondary (result data)

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

Excel

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

To combine with other data

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Decision makers

2 LINKS BETWEEN OUTPUTS

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

a. Yes

CBA

ZENODO

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

DOI

<https://zenodo.org/records/17485288>

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Zenodo

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Dataset – UniProt and RCAAP CBA Case Studies (PathOS Project)

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.1 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA EVEN IF THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CAN NOT BE OPENLY SHARED?

No

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 DO METADATA PROVIDE INFORMATION ABOUT HOW TO ACCESS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.3.4 WILL METADATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER THE DATASET / OUTPUT IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

No

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

No

3.3.3 HAVE YOU APPLIED A STANDARD SCHEMA FOR YOUR (META)DATA?

No

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

no

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

No

1.2.13. Data for Deliverable D1.3 Key Impact Pathways for the Open Science Framework

Data used for development of D1.3 Key Impact Pathways for the Open Science Framework (original and updated version), a deliverable produced within the PathOS Horizon Europe project.

DATASET DESCRIPTION

1 SUMMARY

1.1 BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DESCRIBED RESEARCH OUTPUT

1.1.1 WHAT KIND OF RESEARCH OUTPUT ARE YOU DESCRIBING?

Research Data

1.1.2 IS IT PHYSICAL OR DIGITAL?

Digital

1.1.3 ARE YOU GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

New

1.1.4 WHAT IS THE TYPE OF THE DESCRIBED DATASET?

Derived or compiled

1.1.5 WHAT IS ITS FORMAT?

Spreadsheet format (xlsx)

1.1.6 WHAT IS ITS EXPECTED SIZE?

<1 MB

1.1.7 WHY ARE YOU COLLECTING/GENERATING OR RE-USING IT?

To obtain information

1.1.9 TO WHOM MIGHT IT BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Decision makers

2 LINKS BETWEEN OUTPUTS

2.1 PUBLICATIONS

2.1.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT SUPPORT ANY SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION?

No

2.1.2 IS THERE A DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT PROVIDED ALONG WITH THE PUBLICATION?

No

2.3 SOFTWARE

2.3.1 DOES THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT USE OR SUPPORT ANY SOFTWARE?

No

3 FAIR PRACTICES

3.1 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

3.1.1.1 WHAT TYPE(S) OF PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER(S) ARE USED FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

DOI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16993959>

3.1.1.2 WILL YOU PROVIDE METADATA FOR THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

Yes

Dublin Core

3.1.1.3 WHAT TYPE(S) OF METADATA?

- Descriptive
- Administrative
- Reference
- Legal

3.1.1.4 DO THE METADATA USE STANDARDISED VOCABULARIES?

No

3.1.1.6 ARE THE METADATA SEARCHABLE?

Yes

3.1.1.7 HOW ARE SEARCHABLE METADATA PROVIDED?

Registry/Catalogue

3.1.1.8 ARE KEYWORDS PROVIDED IN THE METADATA?

Yes

3.1.1.9 ARE METADATA HARVESTABLE?

Yes

3.2 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS OPENLY ACCESSIBLE

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

3.2.1.1 IN WHICH REPOSITORY WILL THE DATASET / OUTPUT BE DEPOSITED?

Zenodo

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16993959>

3.2.1.2 IS THE SELECTED REPOSITORY A TRUSTED SOURCE?

Yes

3.2.1.5 DOES THE REPOSITORY(IES) ASSIGN DATASETS / OUTPUTS WITH PERSISTENT IDENTIFIERS?

Yes

3.2.1.7 DOES THE REPOSITORY SUPPORT VERSIONING?

Yes

3.2.2 DATA

3.2.2.1 WHAT IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT TITLE?

Data for Deliverable D1.3 Key Impact Pathways for the Open Science Framework (update)

3.2.2.2 HOW IS THE DATASET / OUTPUT SHARED?

Open

3.2.2.5 ARE THERE ANY METHODS OR TOOLS REQUIRED TO ACCESS THE DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

3.2.2.8 IS THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT SUPPORTED BY A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE?

No

3.2.2.9 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE ACCESSED DURING AND AFTER THE PROJECT ENDS

Open access

3.2.2.10 PLEASE SPECIFY HOW LONG AFTER THE PROJECT HAS ENDED THE DATASET / OUTPUT WILL BE MADE ACCESSIBLE FOR

For the lifetime of the repository (>20 yrs)

3.2.3 METADATA

3.2.3.2 UNDER WHICH LICENSE WILL METADATA BE PROVIDED?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.3 MAKING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS INTEROPERABLE

3.3.1 DOES YOUR (META)DATA USE A CONTROLLED VOCABULARY?

No

3.3.7 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT PROVIDE QUALIFIED REFERENCES WITH OTHER OUTPUTS?

No

3.4 INCREASING DATA AND OTHER OUTPUTS REUSE

3.4.1 WHAT INTERNATIONALLY RECOGNISED LICENCE WILL YOU USE FOR YOUR DATASET / OUTPUT?

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

3.4.3 WILL YOU PROVIDE THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN?

Yes

3.4.4 DO YOU INTEND TO ENSURE (RE)USE BY THIRD PARTIES AFTER YOUR PROJECT FINISHES?

Yes

3.4.5 IS PROVENANCE WELL DOCUMENTED?

Yes

4 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1.1 WHAT WILL BE THE COST OF MAKING THE DESCRIBED OUTPUT FAIR?

- Storage
- Archiving

4.1.2 HOW WILL THIS COST BE COVERED?

Other

6 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1 ETHICAL ASPECTS

6.1.1 ARE THERE ANY ETHICAL OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON SHARING THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT?

No

6.1.2 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN SENSITIVE INFORMATION?

No

6.1.3 DOES THE DESCRIBED DATASET / OUTPUT CONTAIN PERSONAL DATA?

No

7 OTHER ISSUES

7.1 OTHER

7.1.1 DO YOU MAKE USE OF OTHER PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT?

No

Powered by

